

Mapping Protocol: Social-Ecological Vulnerability Mapping, Metropolitan Area of Krakow (V1.0)

Authors: Johannes Langemeyer^a, Svea R. Busse^a, Agnieszka Arabas^b

^a Institute of Environmental Science and Technology, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain

^b Krakow Metropolis Association, Poland

1 Abstract

This protocol details the methodology for spatially explicit social-ecological vulnerability mapping in the Metropolitan Area of Krakow (MK), Poland. It provides a step-by-step guide to data acquisition, processing, and analysis to identify spatial patterns of vulnerabilities, integrating social and ecological sensitivities with exposure to various hazards. The protocol is designed for reproducibility and adaptation to other urban contexts, serving as a tool for planning and

prioritizing nature-based solutions (NBS) to enhance spatial and multispecies justice. The protocol is part of a stepwise, spatial multi-criteria decision analysis developed as part of the INTERLACE project, the method integrates multi-species justice principles into NBS planning. The protocol details the mapping procedure, as step III in a sequence of five steps towards a spatial vulnerability assessment for the prioritization of Nature-Based Solution (See fig.1).

Fig. 1. *Spatial vulnerability assessment for the prioritization of Nature-Based Solution.*

2 Methodology Overview

2.1 Study Area

The Metropolitan Area of Krakow (MK) includes Krakow city and 14 neighbouring municipalities. It spans 1,275 km² and is characterized by diverse urban, peri-urban, and natural landscapes.

2.2 Vulnerability Dimensions

Ten social-ecological vulnerabilities were mapped: lack of recreational opportunities, air pollution, noise pollution, heat stress, river flooding, landslides, wildfires, drought, habitat fragmentation, and biodiversity degradation. Each vulnerability combines exposure and sensitivity indicators.

2.3 Data Preparation

All datasets were projected to ETRS_1989_Poland_CS92. For indicators where the areas outside of the study area impact the outcome (e.g. a park that is located in a bordering municipality adds to the accessibility of green spaces within the MK), the analysis carried out for the study area and a 5 km buffer zone around it. Before the normalization the indicators were clipped to the study area. Unless otherwise stated all operations were carried out in ArcMap 10.8. All raster datasets were created with a 10*10m resolution.

3 Processing Steps

3.1 Vulnerability through lack of recreational opportunities

3.1.1 Walking distance to green spaces up to 0.5 ha

To define green spaces (*green_spaces_recreation.shp*), the land use classes “allotment garden areas”, “forest areas” and “landscaped green spaces” from the Strategy MK 2030 spatial model were merged with the classes “forest” and “park” from Open Street Map (OSM) and “PTLZ” (forest areas) as well as “PTUT01” (allotment gardens) from the official Polish land use data BDOT. The layer was then dissolved (no multi-part features). To define walkable roads (*walkable_roads_osm.shp*), streets classified as “motorway”, “motorway_link”, “trunk” or “trunk_link” were selected and deleted from the OSM street layer. The entry points for green spaces were determined (*green_entry.shp*) by intersecting *green_spaces_recreation.shp* and *walkable_roads_osm.shp*.

To calculate the walking access to areas up to 0.5 ha, a Service area (from layer) was generated in QGIS Hannover, using the *walkable_roads_osm.shp* as the network layer and the *green_entry.shp* as facilities. The shortest path was calculated for 100, 200 and 300 m. In ArcMap again, a Minimum Bounding Geometry with the geometry type CONVEX_HULL was fitted around the service area output line features. The resulting polygons were dissolved and assigned their respective walking distance before transforming and combining them into one single raster file using Polygon to Raster and Mosaic to New Raster. Green spaces were also assigned the value 100, areas further away than 300 m were assigned the value 400.

3.1.2 Walking distance to green spaces above 0.5 ha

Repeat steps from II.I.I. for all features larger than 0.5 ha in *green_spaces_recreation.shp*, now using the following travel distances for the Service area analysis in QGIS: 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, 800, 900, 1000, 1100, 1200. Areas further than 1200 m away from green entry points were assigned the value 1300.

3.1.3 Visibility of green

To determine green areas for visible access the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) on a 10 m resolution was calculated from a Sentinel 2 scene recorded on 23th of June 2022 at 9:50:34 UTC using the semi-automatic classification plugin in QGIS. All pixels with a NDVI higher than 0.38 were classified as green, this threshold was determined by comparison with true colour orthoimages. With Raster to Polygon simplified polygons of all “green” areas were created. Within these polygons, random points were created, assuring at least one point per polygon, and additional of points per 0.25 ha (*green_vis_sample.shp*). The assigned number of sample points for the visibility analysis is a compromise made to reduce processing time.

A digital surface model (DSM) in the PL-KRON89-NH elevation system with a resolution of 0.5 – 1 m was retrieved from geoportal.gov.pl, in the study area the data was collected between 2011 and 2017. The ASCII files were exported to a 32-bit floating raster at a 10 m resolution, as previous attempts with a higher resolution failed due to missing computing capacity.

With the ArcMap Viewshed 2 tool, the visibility from each point in the DSM to the *green_vis_sample.shp* as observer points was calculated at a surface offset of 1.6 m to model visibility at eye level (Analysis method: ALL_SIGHTLINES, Analysis type: FREQUENCY, Refractivity coefficient: 0.13). The outer radius of the viewshed analysis was set at 1500 meters, assuming that the beneficial effects of greenery further away is negligible (Tabrizian et al. 2020). Due to the large computing capacity required, this operation was run in 27 batches that were combined with Mosaic to Raster (Mosaic Operator: SUM). Pixels with a higher frequency than 359, which are 10% of all pixels, were assigned the value 360. Then the raster was normalized.

The resulting raster was combined with the green areas (as determined by the NDVI), which were assigned the value 1.

3.1.4 Visibility of blue

The same procedure as for the visibility of green was repeated for the visibility of blue spaces. Here the BDOT land use class “PTWP” (water bodies) was used as an input for the first step. These polygons were aggregated at 1m to simplify polygons as larger water bodies were split in several features, before assigning the sampling points as described above. Again, a cut-off value was set at the 90% percentile (40 in this case), before normalizing the raster.

3.1.5 Distance to non-green recreation

As non-green recreational facilities, the OSM points on interest with the fclass “dog_park”, “playground”, “pitch”, “sports_center”, “stadium”, “swimming pool” and “picnic_site” were extracted. With the Euclidean Distance tool, a 1200 m decaying buffer was placed around sites.

3.1.6 Percentage of population below 14 years

The population count and demographic structure for the year 2011 was provided by the Polish Statistical Office in 1km² polygons.

3.1.7 Percentage of population receiving social assistance

The share population receiving social benefits from the state in the year 2021 was provided by Statistics Poland (2021, 2021) in the Local Data Bank (bdl.stat.gov.pl).

3.1.8 Percentage of unemployed population in the working age

The share of registered unemployment in the year 2021 was provided by Statistics Poland (2021) in the Local Data Bank (bdl.stat.gov.pl).

3.1.9 Population density

See 3.1.6.

3.2 Vulnerability to air pollution

3.2.1 Average concentration of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂

The average concentration of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂ were prepared and provided the European Environment Agency (EEA) (2022) for a resolution of 1 km². The data was resampled to a 10 m resolution using a bilinear resampling technique.

3.2.2 Distance to elementary schools

From the Strategy MK 2030 Spatial Model, the point features “Szkoly_podstawowe_gminy_MK” and „szkoly_branzowe_Krakow” were merged (*elementary_schools.shp*). Following the findings of Porebski et al. (2014), a Euclidean distance buffer with a maximum distance of 500 m was placed around the *elementary_schools.shp*, using major roads (SKDR01-SKDR04 from BDOT) as barriers.

3.2.3 Distance to playgrounds

The OSM points of interest with the fclass “playgrounds” were extracted and then repeat the procedure as described in 3.2.2.

3.2.4 Percentage of population above 65 years

See 3.1.6.

3.2.5 Distance to health & care facilities

To identify the facilities, OSM points of interest with the fclass “doctors” were merged with the points from the BDOT class “KUOZ” (health and social care complex). Than the steps in II.II.II where repeated.

3.3 Vulnerability to noise pollution

3.3.1 Traffic noise level above 50 dB

To estimate the noise immission from traffic sources in the whole study area, the distances for the noise classes differentiated by street class or rail type were measured for the day time imission layers of the noise map of Krakow (City of Krakow 2017). (Hałas drogowy LDWN, Hałas kolejowy LDWN and Hałas tramwajowy LDWN). Each street class, as well as tram and railway lines from the Strategy MK 2030 spatial model were buffered accordingly (see Table 2). The buffer polygons were turned into raster and the layers of major roads and railway lines were mosaiced with the official noise maps reported under EU requirements.

All individual noise sources (L_i) where then combined using the following equation (2) following Sivertun (2012):

$$L = 10 \text{Log}_{10} \sum_{i=1}^n 10^{(L_i/10)} \quad (2)$$

The resulting combined traffic noise levels were normalized between 0 and 80 dB.

	Motorways (Street class A)	Expressways and main roads of accelerated traffic (Street classes GP & S)	Main roads (Street class G)	Collector roads (Street class Z)	Local roads (Street class L)	Tram	Railway
> 75 dB	50 m	28 m	5 m	2 m			5 m
75 dB	90 m	60 m	25 m	23 m	10	3 m	15 m
70 dB	140 m	120 m	45 m	35 m	18	15 m	25 m
65 dB	235 m	210 m	90 m	50 m	40	35 m	70 m
60 dB	360 m	340 m	145 m	80 m	70 m	75 m	150 m
55 dB	480 m	430 m	285 m	100 m	90 m	100 m	350 m

3.3.2 Land use sensitivity

Following Ministerstwo Środowiska (2007) the noise sensitivity was differentiated by land-use as displayed bellow:

Classification according to Ministerstwo Środowiska (2007) https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20140000112/O/D20140112.pdf	Realization in GIS	Permitted mean sound level from roads & railway	Normalized sensitivity
Protection zone A, health resorts, hospital areas outside the city	All BDOT PT (“land cover”) intersecting with KUOZ (“health and social care complex”) and not intersecting with the municipality of Krakow.	50	1
Single-family housing areas, development areas related to the permanent or temporary stay of children and adolescent, social care homes, hospital areas in cities	BDOT PTZB02 (“single-family housing”) All BDOT PT (“land cover”) intersecting with Elementary Schools MK from the Strategy MK 2030 Spatial Model All BDOT PT (“land cover”) intersecting with KUOZ (“health and social care complex”) and intersecting with the municipality of Krakow.	64	0.53
Areas for multi-family housing and collective housing, areas for farm buildings, recreation and leisure areas, residential and service areas	BDOT PTZB01 (“multifamily housing”) Urban Atlas (European Environment Agency (EEA) 2018b) land use shapefile: Sports and leisure facilities; Forests; Green urban areas BDOT PTZB04 (“commercial and service buildings”)	68	0.4

3.4 Vulnerability to heat

3.4.1 Heat islands above 30°C

To identify heat islands, the surface temperature during a heat wave was estimated using Landsat 8 imagery following Sobrino et al. (2004) and Avdan and Jovanovska (2016). Download Landsat 8 Bands 4,5, and 10 for the 07.08.2013 via the Semi-automated classification Plugin in QGIS and clip to study area. The following steps were conducted using the raster calculator.

- Calculate top of atmosphere (TAO) (Avdan and Jovanovska 2016)

$$0.0003342 * \text{Landsat 8 07.08.2013\LC08_L1TP_188025_20130807_20170503_01_T1_2013-08-07_B10_clip.TIF} +$$

$$0.1 - 0.29 = \text{toa.tif}$$

- Calculate Brightness temperature in °C (**bt**) (Avdan and Jovanovska 2016)

$$(1321.0789 / \text{Ln} ((774.8853 / \text{"Heat\toa.tif"}) + 1)) - 273.15 = \text{bt.tif}$$

- Calculate **NDV** (Avdan and Jovanovska 2016; Sobrino et al. 2004)

$$\frac{\text{Float}(\text{Band 5} - \text{Band 4})}{\text{Float}(\text{Band 5} + \text{Band 4})} = \text{ndvi.tif}$$

- Calculate the proportion of vegetation (**Pv**) (Sobrino et al. 2004)

$$\text{Square} \left(\frac{\text{ndvi_clip} - (-0.178611)}{0.615805 - (-0.178611)} \right) = \text{pv.tif}$$

- Calculate Emissivity (**E**) (Sobrino et al. 2004)

$$0.004 * \text{"Pv"} + 0.986 = \text{E.tif}$$

- Calculate land Surface temperature (LST):

$$(\text{"bt.tif"} / (1 + (0.00115 * \text{"bt.tif"} / 1.4388) * \text{Ln}(\text{"E.tif"}))) = \text{LST_MK.tif}$$

The resulting raster was resampled with Nearest neighbour technique to 10x10m resolution and normalized between the maximum (43.6°C) and 30°C, assigning 0 to all pixels below that threshold.

3.5 Vulnerability to river flooding and runoff

3.5.1 Fluvial flood risk

Flood hazard maps were obtained from the Polish Water Holdings (Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie n.d.a). The following layers were combined in one raster:

Hazard class	Normalized Exposure
Flood hazard with 0.2% probability (Zasięg MZP od rzek-0,2%(raz na 500 lat))	0.02
Flood hazard with 1% probability (Zasięg MZP od rzek-0,2%(raz na 100 lat))	0.1
Flood hazard with 10% probability (Zasięg MZP od rzek-0,2%(raz na 10 lat))	1
Areas with no flood hazard	0

3.5.2 Run-off coefficient

The run-off coefficient was calculated following Cecchi et al. (2007). Instead of CORINE land use data, the more detailed BDOT classes were used. Following Langemeyer et al. (2020) the permeability was averaged for each land use class. The following values were assigned and combined in the raster "permeability.tif"

CORINE Code_18	CORINE land cover class used in Cecchi et al. (2007)	BDOT x_kod	BDOT Description	Average Permeability
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111	Continuous urban fabric	PTZB01	multi-family housing	0.86
112	Discontinuous urban fabric	PTZB02	single-family housing	0.74
		PTZB05	remaining buildings	0.8
121	Industrial or commercial units	PTZB03; PTZB04; PTNZ02; PTNZ01	industrial and storage buildings; commercial and service buildings; industrial and storage area; area under technical devices or	0.9175
122	Road and rail networks and associated land	PTKM01; PTKM02; PTKM03; PTPL01	area under the road; area under track; area under the road and track; place	0.98
124	Airports	PTKM04	area under the airport road	0.8825
131	Mineral extraction Sites	PTWZ01	excavation	0.695
132	Dump Sites	PTWZ02; PTSO01; PTSO02	dump; municipal waste storage area; industrial waste storage area	0.695
141	Green urban areas	PTLZ03	trees	0.635
142	Sport and leisure facilities	PTUT01	garden allotment	0.635
211	Non-irrigated arable land	PTTR02; PTUT05	cultivation on arable land; nursery of ornamental plants	0.815
222	Fruit trees and berry plantations	PTUT02; PTUT03	plantation; court	0.6775
244	Agro-forestry areas	PTLZ02	copse	0.6775
313	Mixed forest	PTLZ01	forest	0.62
321	Natural grasslands	PTTR01	grassy vegetation	0.7025
324	Transitional woodland-shrub	PTRK02; PTUT04	shrubs; forest nursery	0.62
331	Beaches. dunes. sands	PTGN03	sandy or gravel ground	0.8525
333	Sparsely vegetated areas	PTGN04	remaining unused land	0.7025
511	Water courses	PTWP02	flowing water	1
512	Water bodies	PTWP03	stagnant water	1
523	Sea and ocean	PTWP01	sea water	1

A digital terrain model (DTM) was reclassified according to the slope correction coefficient in Cecchi et al. (2007) and saved as "slope_cor.tif". The runoff coefficient was calculated as follows:

$$\text{permeability.tif} * \text{slope_cor.tif} = \text{runoff_coef.tif}$$

3.5.3 Critical infrastructure

As critical infrastructure the following features were selected, adapted from the Polish flood risk maps (Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie n.d.b).

- Strategy MK 2030 Spatial Model:
 - Main streets (street class A, S, G, GP)
 - Main train lines (class Z)
- Open Street Map Points of interest:
 - “atm”, “embassy”, “fire_station”, “lighthouse”, “police”, “supermarket”, “town_hall”, “doctors”, “pharmacy”

All features were buffered with 100 m, assuming that an impact closer than this distance would put the functioning and reachability of the infrastructure at risk.

3.6 Vulnerability to landslides

3.6.1 Landslide risk

The risk of mass movement was prepared and provided by the Polish Geological Institute (2015).

The following exposure values were assigned:

Shapefile	Description	Assigned normalized exposure value
SOPO_GIS_OSUWISKA_POW.shp	Active	1
	Periodically active	0.75
	Inactive	0.5
SOPO_GIS_OBSZARY_ZAGROZONE.shp	Prone to masse movement	0.25
	All other areas	0

3.7 Vulnerability to wildfires

3.7.1 Wild fire risk

The Fire Weather Index (FWI) was prepared and provided by Nykiel, Figurski (2020) on a 1 km² resolution. The mean of the daily FWI values given for the period from March to September 2019 the was calculated. The data was resampled using the nearest neighbour method.

3.7.2 Areas under nature conservation

Following the IUCN (2008) classification, protected areas extracted from the Strategy MK 2030 Spatial model were assigned the following values:

Description	IUCN classification	Sensitivity value
National parks	II	1
Natura 2000 areas; nature reserves	IV	0.5
Landscape parks	V	0.25

All other areas	No classification	0
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3.8 Vulnerability to drought

3.8.1 Soil moisture content

The soil moisture content in percent at 0-10 cm depth was also provided by Nykiel, Figurski (2020) on a 1 km² resolution. Again, for the period from March to September 2019 the mean was calculated. The data was resampled using the nearest neighbour method.

3.8.2 Areas of food production

To determine the areas of food production, the BDOT land use classes “PTUT01” (allotment), “PTUT02” (plantation), “PTUT03” (orchard) and “PTTR02” (arable land cultivation) were selected. After comparison with orthoimagery, also polygons of the class “PTUT01” (grass vegetation) were added when intersecting with the CORINE (2018) land use class “2” (agricultural areas). All selected areas off food production were assigned the value 1, all other areas 0.

3.9 Vulnerability to habitat fragmentation

3.9.1 Land use friction for pollinators

Friction values were assigned to different land use polygons following Johansson et al. (2018):

Land use classes used by Johansson et al. (2018)	BDOT class and realization in GIS	Friction value
Food habitat: Grasslands and shrub-lands with low intensity management; Edges of forests and fields; Bedrock outcrops; Home gardens classified as ‘lush’ and areas with cultivation of fruits and berries (e.g. allotments)	PTTR01 Grassy vegetation, when interesectioning with Strategy MK 2030 Spatial Model land use class "Undevelopped green areas", PTRK02 shrubs 10 Meter outer buffer around PTLZ01 Forests and PTTR02 Cultivation on agricultural lands, - PTUT01 Garden allotment, PTUT03 Orchards, PTUT05 Nursery of ornamental plants	1
Intensively managed grasslands	PTTR01 Grassy vegetation (when not interesectioning with <i>Model 2030</i> landuse class "Undevelopped green areas")	2
Lawns	All remaining areas with an NDVI > 0.38 as determined in II.I.III.	5
Home gardens not classified as "lush"		5
Vegetation covered water	-	10

Arable land	PTTR02 Cultivation on arable land PTUT02 Plantation PTUT04 Forest nursery	10
Mires	-	5
Scarce Forests (<70% crown cover)	PTLZ02 Copse PTLZ03 Trees PTRK01 Mountain pine	5
Dense forests (>80% crown cover)	PTLZ01 Forest	15
Small roads	-	5
Intermediate roads	Urban Atlas land use class "Other Roads and associated land"	20
Large roads	Urban Atlas land use class "Fast transit roads and associated land"	50
Railroads	Urban Atlas land use class "Railways and associated land"	15
Paved ground (other than roads)	PTPL01 Square All remaining areas with an NDVI < 0.38	50
Buildings	Open Street Map Buildings	1000
Small open water (Small dams and streams)	PTWP and OSM Water where Area/Perimeter < 5	5
Large open water (Lakes and the sea)	PTWP and OSM Water where Area/Perimeter >= 5	100

3.9.2 Main ecological corridors

A shapefile of potential major ecological corridors for the prioritized establishment of greenery was prepared for the Strategy MK 2030 Spatial Model (Metropolia Krakowska 2021c).

3.10 Vulnerability to biodiversity degradation

3.10.1 Biodiversity intactness

The biodiversity intactness index was provided by Scholes and Biggs (2005) on a 1 km² resolution. The data was resampled using the nearest neighbor technique.

3.10.2 Areas under nature conservation

Following the argumentation laid out in chapter 3.3.10 the indicator as described in 3.7.2 was used but with inverse sensitivity values.

Description	IUCN classification	Sensitivity value
National parks	II	0
Natura 2000 areas; nature reserves	IV	0.5

Landscape parks	V	0.75
All other areas	No classification	1

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